



Response curves of important environmental variables for *S. angustifolium* (A-C), *S. fuscum* (D-F), *S. magellanicum s. lato* (G-I), *S. rubellum* (J-L), *S. papillosum* (M-O), and *S. cuspidatum* (P-R).